

The Information Flow Methodology (IFM)

User Guide

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1 Introduction to the Information Flow Methodology (IFM)

The Information Flow Methodology (IFM) is a structured way to describe and analyze how decisions are made in socio-technical systems. It models a decision as a transformation of information—showing where information comes from, how it is interpreted or processed, and how it leads to an outcome. By representing decisions in this way, IFM makes the underlying structure, assumptions, and dependencies of a process explicit.

While IFM captures the structure of information and how it is transformed in decision-making, it is not intended to model every aspect of system behavior or process control. Temporal order, iteration, and detailed task execution are outside its present scope and may be represented through complementary modeling approaches when needed.

Unlike traditional process maps or modeling notations such as BPMN or UML, which represent activities, control flows, or system components, IFM focuses on the *structure of information* that underlies decision-making. It describes how inputs are combined, transformed, and interpreted to produce outcomes, regardless of whether these transformations are performed by humans or automated systems. By emphasizing dependencies between information rather than procedural steps, IFM reveals how decisions are formed, what they rely on, and where responsibility or uncertainty resides. IFM models do not focus on components in isolation but rather on their integration within a holistic view of the decision process, thereby avoiding framing traps common in component-level AI evaluation.

The methodology can be applied in several ways, but a central design goal is to support participatory modeling. In this approach, the people who develop, perform, or oversee parts of the decision process are directly involved in constructing the model. Through this engagement, stakeholders collaboratively identify what information matters, how they interpret and use it, and how outcomes are ultimately produced. Participatory modeling ensures that IFM models capture the *actual* decision-making structure of an organization—including informal practices, tacit judgments, and contextual dependencies.

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Originally developed to support AI transparency, IFM has been extended to analyze bias, fairness, accountability, and impact in socio-technical systems. It is particularly useful in settings where decisions arise from multiple roles, systems, or layers of information—such as AI procurement or EU AI Act compliance assessment. By revealing how human and automated steps interact, IFM provides *structural insight*: it shows how decision points, constraints, uncertainties, and accountability connect into a whole, making it a practical foundation for audits, impact assessments, stakeholder dialogue, and governance of complex systems.

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Who is this guide for?

This guide is intended for anyone involved in analyzing, designing, or reviewing decision systems that combine human and automated elements. It may be especially useful for:

- Public authorities and procurement teams evaluating the use of AI or automated decision support in sensitive domains.
- Auditors and assessors responsible for examining how systems align with legal, ethical, or institutional requirements.
- Civil society organizations and advocacy groups seeking to understand or question how decisions are made, where power lies, and what risks are present.
- Developers and researchers aiming to better capture how their systems are used in practice and how they affect different stakeholders.

2 Core Concepts

In the IFM Methodology, a decision process is described as a flow of **information** through a network of **sites** and **channels**. A combination of input sites and output sites connected by a channel describes what a decision or transformation is based on (the input sites), what it results in (the output sites), and what the transformation itself is (the channel). This is the minimal unit from which all IFM models are constructed.

In this section, we introduce these basic building blocks and describe how they are used. These concepts form the foundation for describing how decisions are made, how information moves, and where responsibilities and risks arise.

2.1 Sites, Channels and Networks

The two fundamental elements of an information flow model are *sites* and *channels*:

- A **site** is a place or stage where information exists. It could represent an input, a completed form, a document, a score, a decision, a dataset, or any intermediate result in a process.
- A **channel** is a transformation or decision that moves or changes information from one site to another. Channels include operations such as filtering, scoring, classification, interpretation, or judgment. Each channel connects one or more *upstream input sites* to one or more *downstream output sites*, and captures the logic or activity that changes the state of information.

Together, sites and channels describe how information flows through a decision process—from the most *upstream* inputs to the final *downstream* outcomes. A system of connected sites and channels is called an information *network*.

In a network, the following rules must be upheld:

- No output from a channel can be the input of a channel *upstream* (earlier in the process). In other words, the network must not contain loops.
- The inputs to a channel should be sufficient to produce the outputs, given the transformation it performs.

Following these rules ensures that a network forms a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG) from inputs to outputs. Even a single channel with its inputs and outputs constitutes a network. Conversely, any network can be treated as a single channel representing the full transformation from the most upstream inputs to the most downstream outputs.

Any channel can also be detailed further by expanding it into a full sub-network of sites and channels. This makes IFM models *nestable*, allowing them to be abstracted or refined to a suitable level of detail. Nesting also supports modularity: different parts of a decision process — such as an AI tool — can be modeled separately and later integrated into a combined structure.

In diagrams, sites are typically text labels, and channels as arrows connecting them. The direction of the arrow follows the flow of information—from upstream inputs to downstream results. Channels can be presented one by one with their sites or connected together into a network graph. Sites only participating in a flow as reference material or other assisting information to a channel can be marked as [*site*], such sites are termed as *static* sites.

Example:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{[Eligibility Criteria]} & \xrightarrow{\text{Eligibility Check}} & \text{Eligibility Result} \\ \text{Application} & & \end{array}$$

Here, *Eligibility Check* represents a channel that takes the *Application* as input and produces the *Eligibility Result* using the static *Eligibility Criteria*.

2.2 Types and Typing

Each site and channel in an IFM model has a **type** that indicates what kind of information it holds or transforms.

- A **site type** *Ex. S1: text* specifies what kind of information a site contains — such as *text*, *score*, *decision*, or *category*.
- A **channel type** *C1: filtering* specifies the kind of transformation it performs — such as *scoring*, *classification*, or *filtering*.

In this guide types will be handled rather informally. What types to use and how detailed they should be depends on what is modeled. The purpose here is clarity. Like with other aspects of IFM, types can be made almost arbitrarily detailed. It is up to the modeler to select a degree of detail fitting with the analysis or purpose.

While sites are unique, types are not. Often the channel type is at least partially implied by the site types, and in turn the channel type suggest an envelope of possible bias based upon how such a transformation can go wrong. A suggested list of channel types in relation to bias will be presented in relation to modeling Step 3 and 4.

$$S1: \text{ text } \xrightarrow{C1: \text{ summary}} S2: \text{ text } \xrightarrow{C2: \text{ translation}} S3: \text{ text, english}$$

In this case, all three sites hold textual information, but each represents a distinct stage in the information flow.

2.3 Alternatives and Uncertainty

Many real-world systems have variability. Sometimes a part of a procedure is added or omitted. Even the modeling process may involve uncertainty. In IFM this can be modeled through the use of *alternatives*.

Alternatives represent several possible configurations such as whether a human or AI evaluates an input, or whether certain information is used for the decision or not. Alternatives can apply to sites, channels, or entire sub-networks. They are used to model design options, ambiguities, or bias. During assessment, alternatives can be used to reason about possible scenarios, compare configurations, or surface hidden assumptions.

By incorporating alternatives, IFM supports structured exploration of uncertainty and variation — whether arising from technical systems, human judgment, or institutional processes.

The purpose of IFM modeling is usually not to capture all fine grained variability that exist in a decision process but rather understand how the general structure contribute to various effects, thus alternatives should not be seen as a necessary tool to capture minute detail but rather a tool that makes modeling of particular alternative paths of interest possible.

In diagrams, alternatives are prefixed by a question mark (?) and either as ?*A*, meaning *A* might not be there, or as ?{*A|B*}, meaning *A* and *B* are potential alternatives.

Example:

$$[\text{Eligibility Criteria}] \quad \xrightarrow{\text{Eligibility Check}} \quad \text{Eligibility} \quad \xrightarrow{? \text{Reference Check}} \quad \text{Eligibility Result}$$

$$?\{\text{Application|Personal Request}\} \quad \xrightarrow{\text{Eligibility Check}} \quad ?\text{References}$$

The example above illustrates that the Eligibility Check might sometimes depend on a Personal Request rather than an Application. Further, sometimes there is no Reference Check.

2.4 Bias and Impact

In the IFM framework, both **bias** and **impact** are treated as structural properties of the modeled decision process. They represent different but related unwanted effects in a decision process which might cause errors, affect individuals or groups, or violate regulatory obligations.

Bias refers to a systematic deviation from the described or intended function of the decision process. It can manifest as inaccurate or unjustified outcomes—such as false positives or false negatives, possibly disproportionately as affecting certain subgroups. Bias is introduced within channels or already present in the information as a site, and can propagate *downstream* through dependent sites and channels. Any downstream channel that uses a biased site as input can potentially act as a proxy for that bias. Conversely, if the biased information is not used or its influence is mitigated, the propagation path terminates.

This directional structure allows assessors to trace how bias emerges and spreads through the network, and to evaluate whether mitigating mechanisms effectively contain it.

Impact, in contrast, refers to the real-world consequences or risks produced by a decision process — especially unintended or harmful effects on stakeholders. While bias is one potential source of harmful impact, impacts may also arise even when the system behaves as designed, if its construction failed to account for certain risks, contexts, or stakeholder perspectives.

Impacts typically appear at the downstream ends of an IFM network. Understanding their causes requires tracing *upstream* through the information flow to identify contributing decisions and informational transformations.

Where a path downstream from bias intersects with a tracing upstream from impact, the bias may be a contributing cause of the impact. In some cases, impacts only affect specific individuals or subgroups. To analyze these cases, it may be necessary to trace identifiers, attributes, or proxy variables linked to the subgroup through the flow. This can help determine whether such features contributed to the harm.

By modeling both bias and impact explicitly, IFM supports structured analysis of how harms arise, how they may be mitigated, and whether responsibilities are properly aligned with control and influence in the system.

In principle, any bias can also be represented as an *alternative* sub-network that highlights the structural deviation responsible for it. Modeling bias in this way can clarify how it contributes to downstream impacts, how it might be mitigated, or how the risk of impact could be reduced through structural changes.

2.5 Orthogonal networks: Structuring of IFM models

In many practical cases the relevant process to model is not just one information flow but several interconnected networks where one produces the other. This is commonly seen in situations where there is a setup process that configures or primes the process one actually wants to study. One possibility here is to just model the final process and use *static* sites to represent the configuration. But in order to understand the effects of bias *across* such systems it is beneficial to model both of them as *orthogonal* networks where some of the sites that are static, or even channels in one IFM network, are outputs of the other IFM network. Here is one example, another can be seen in the more detailed example in Section 3.

Example:

Training: $\left[\text{Dataset: Features} \times \text{Labels} \xrightarrow{\text{Learning Function}} \text{Model } M: \text{Features} \rightarrow \text{Labels} \right]$

Classification: $\left[\text{Document: Features} \xrightarrow{M} \text{Document class: Labels} \right]$

This describes a typical classifier setup: a model M is trained on a dataset and later used to classify new documents. In IFM terms, the *Training* flow produces the model M , which becomes a *channel* in the downstream *Classification* flow. Modeling these flows together allows us to reason about the assumptions, data dependencies, and evaluation paths across learning and deployment.

3 Example IFM

To illustrate what a complete IFM model may look like in practice, the following figure presents a real modeling case. The model depicts a recruitment process and combines multiple interconnected networks on two levels of abstraction, including a sourcing process that produces structured profiles (top) and a screening process that compares candidates to these profiles (bottom), both of these processes are nested within the single arrow in the client process (center).

#	Transition	Actor	Sub-Network	Bias/(Mitigation)	Impact
a	Client $\xrightarrow{\text{AI Profile + Rec}}$ $R0, R1, R2$	Recruiter	Client process	Interpretation, (Normalization)	I1, I2 (client, rec)
b	$R0, R1, X \xrightarrow{\text{AI Match}}$ $C0_b$	AI	Sourcing	Opacity	I3, I4 (age, location)
c	$R0, R1, X \xrightarrow{\text{LinkedIn, other}}$ $C0_c$	Recruiter	Sourcing	Interpretation	
d	$R2, \text{Candidate DB} \xrightarrow{\text{DB search}}$ $C0_d$	Recruiter	Sourcing	Interpretation ($R2$)	
e	$[R0, R2], C0_b, C0_c, C0_d \xrightarrow{\text{Rec. filter}}$ $C1$	Recruiter	Screening	Presentation, ("Human-in-the-loop")	
f	$C1 \xrightarrow{\text{Call}}$ $[R2], \text{Impression} \xrightarrow{\text{Rec. filter}}$ $C2$	Recruiter	Screening	Interpretation ($R2$)	
g	$C2 \xrightarrow{\text{Interview}}$ $[R1, R2], \text{Soft skills} \xrightarrow{\text{Rec. filter}}$ $C3$	Recruiter	Screening	Interpretation ($R2$)	
h	$C3 \xrightarrow{\text{Client Selection}}$ $C4$	Client	Client process	Interpretation, Presentation	I1 (client)

Table 1: Recruitment system transitions with actor roles, biases, and downstream impacts

Figure 1 displays a simplified view of the full graph with focus on highlighting the most relevant aspects of the information flow. Each channel is lettered and presented with more information in Table 1. In the table, each channel is annotated with what sub-network it belongs to, who is the responsible stakeholder and potential bias and bias mitigation. In addition there are three paths from bias to impacts identified focusing on discriminatory effects. $I1$ represents bias derived from the client, $I2$ bias on the side of the recruiter, in particular tied to site $R2$, and $I3$ represents bias due to the AI model in the AI matching channel. Each of these sources of bias can propagate through the information flow downstream to reach stakeholder impacts.

This model will be used as a running example in the step-wise methodology below.

Figure 1: Overview of the recruitment process information flow corresponding to Table 1. The included dashed green box displays the client process in where the channels a-g) is embedded.

4 Modeling methodology: Stepwise Construction of the Information Flow Model

The IFM methodology is applied through a six-step modeling process. These steps guide the construction and analysis of an information flow model, from initial sketching to identifying risks and evaluating outcomes. Each step builds on the previous, allowing both technical and non-technical participants to contribute meaningfully. The process is designed to support collaborative modeling, traceability, and reflection across roles and domains.

Stakeholders play a vital role in this process and the process is designed to allow participatory involvement, especially early. It is recommended to use interviews or workshops to:

- Capture the stakeholders view on the process and what it does.
- Ensure the model captures the real-world decision-making process.
- Understand what aspects are important and appropriate level of detail.
- Uncover variation in perspectives among stakeholders.
- Validate the accuracy of the scaffold and refined model.

The process is intended to be modifiable depending on use case, mode and availability of information. The guide should be seen as a rough frame where the emphasis put on a particular step can be varied depending on the requirements of the case at hand.

Step 1: Sketching the Information Flow

The first step is to create a sketched *scaffold* of the decision process you want to analyze. This sketch should capture the overall structure of how information flows — what enters the process, how it changes, and what final decision or outcome it leads to. The goal is not precision or formal correctness but to capture the overall structure in broad terms, facilitating stakeholder engagement and input as well as overview. Follow these steps four general steps:

I. Define the Scope of the Decision Process

- **What decision or process is being modeled?** Clearly state the boundaries and purpose.
- **Start and End Points:** Identify where the flow begins (e.g., data entry, initial request) and ends (e.g., decision, output, action).
- *Example: We are modeling a recruitment process. It starts with a request from a client and ends when a set of candidate profiles is delivered back.*

II. Identify initial Sites and Channels

- What information is used throughout the process? This includes documents, forms and decisions. These represent **Sites**. If they are changed during the process each state represents it's own Site.
- What decisions, evaluations, calculations and transformations are part of this process? These are **Channels** and connect Sites together.
- **Channels** represent transformations between sites—decisions, filtering steps, interviews, or automated evaluations.
- Use descriptive names for sites and channels which reflect how each element would be understood by stakeholders.
- *Example: "Initial candidates" and "Final candidates" could be sites; "Recruiter filter based on Interview." and "DB search" could be channels.*

III. Map the Decision Process

- From the initial sites and channels, start looking at known intermediary steps. What transformations occur between the start and end points? Break these steps into sites and channels.
- Ask stakeholders to describe the process and the steps they take. Note down each step.
- Ask, how do you perform this step? What does it result in?

- Name each site and channel descriptively to make the model understandable to stakeholders using the terms they use.

IV. Construct the Initial Graph

- Arrange sites and channels into a draft graph. Focus on clarity over precision.
- Sketches can be based on interviews, documentation, system behavior, or stakeholder narratives.
- Different sketches from different perspectives may coexist and be compared or merged later.
- *Example: The process might include “Initial candidates” → “Filtered Candidates” → “Interview Outcomes” → “Final Suggestions.”*

Result of steps I: One or several scaffolds of the information flow model, showing the decision process loosely expressed as named sites and channels.

Step 2: Refining the Information Flow Model

In this step, the initial scaffold is refined to provide a more detailed and precise representation of the decision process. This involves examining *each channel individually* to understand its dependencies, outputs, and potential ambiguities.

I. Analyze Each Channel For each channel C from source sites (A) to target sites (B) in the model:

- Consider what (A) and (B) consist of. Are they documents, scores, subjective understanding. What possible values could they take? Noting this down at least informally helps both this step and the next (step 4).
- **Describe the Process:** Clearly articulate how information flows from the source sites (A) to the target sites (B). Include any intermediate transformations.
- **Verify Outputs:** Does sites (B) contain information which is not an output of this channel C ? Remove any extraneous information.
- **Verify Input Sufficiency:** Is the information in sites (A) sufficient to produce site (B)? If not, what additional inputs are required (e.g., reference information, rules, datasets)?
- Amend the model by adding intermediate sites or inputs as needed, possibly as *static* sites showing that they do not change here but shape the decision-making.

II. Address Ambiguities and Alternatives

- **Identify Ambiguities:** Are there areas where the process is unclear or where multiple interpretations are possible?
- **Represent Alternatives:** If decisions can be made in different ways or with different inputs, consider to include these alternatives explicitly in the model.

III. Ensure Model Validity When each of the channels have been treated individually, consider how they fit together.

- Ensure the graph remains a directional graph, with clear pathways from inputs to final decisions without loops.
- If loops seem to exist, consider:

- Splitting the IFM into several orthogonal information flows.
- Merging channels which together can not be seen as a transformation from A to B until they can.
- Marking feedback dynamics as sources of potential bias on particular channels or sites
 - For step 4.
- Use abstraction to simplify overly detailed sections of the graph. For example, group related sub-networks into a single channel if they represent one functional step. Several abstraction levels of the same channel or sub-network can be kept and used as needed.

*Example: The graph in Figure 1 together with the leftmost column of Table 1 describe a possible output of Step 2. **Result:** A refined and detailed formally valid IFM that accurately reflects the decision process, capturing information-dependencies and ambiguities.*

Step 3: Assigning Types and Semantic Roles

With the IFM scaffold refined, this step involves assigning descriptive types to each site and channel to classify the kinds of information they represent and the transformations they undergo. Follow these steps:

I. Classify Site Types For each channel C from source sites (A) to target sites (B) in the model:

- Assign descriptive types to the sites (A) and (B), starting with broad classifications:
 - **Structured or Unstructured:** Identify whether the information is structured (e.g., datasets with defined fields) or unstructured (e.g., free text, images).
 - **Lists and Sub-lists:** Determine whether the site contains collections of items (lists) or filtered subsets (sub-lists).
- Refine these classifications as needed, depending on domain-specific requirements. Ideally describe the type of information in a way recognizable to stakeholders and which also says something about which possible values a site could take.
- Subjective or unstructured information might not be strictly described but can be contained in a looser description. Doing so still assist coming steps.

II. Describe Channel Transformations from Site Types For each channel C from source sites (A) to target sites (B) in the model:

- Use the input and output types of a channel to say something about what kind of transformation it represents.
- Identify if the transformation represents filtering, ranking, aggregation, abstraction, or interpretation.
- Attempt to make clear how each site of information participates to create the output.

III. Give Semantic Descriptions to Important Sub-Networks

- Identify meaningful sub-networks of the graph. These are chains of sites and channels that perform a distinct function in the overall process.
- Assign each such sub-network a short, descriptive name (e.g., *Initial Screening*, *Automated Matching*, *Evaluation*).

- These named sub-networks help orient the model, support stakeholder dialogue, and anchor later bias or impact analysis.

Result: A typed information flow model that provides structured classifications of sites and channels, enabling deeper analysis of potential biases.

Step 4: Identifying and Mapping Biases

This step examines the typed IFM for potential biases introduced by transformations. In general consider the transformation type and the information of each channel and consider the ways this might go wrong. If the analysis to be done focus on particular risks it might be necessary to keep that in mind and iteratively examine the interaction between bias and impact (Step 5).

Among other, attention should be given to the following situations: **I. Consider Channel Specific Bias**

- **Information Loss:** Abstract representations may fail to capture the richness of original data.
- **Unintended Information:** Implicit information (e.g., order in a list) may unintentionally influence outcomes.
- **Blocked Channels:** Situations where intended processes are unrealizable without additional resources or information.
- **Unintended Channels:** Alternate pathways that bypass the formal decision process.
- **Pre-existing Bias:** External biases already in input sites can influence decisions where this information is involved.

II. Represent Bias in the IFM

- Map potential biases to specific sites or channels.
- Consider to describe key biases as alternative channels in the IFM to make the bias explicitly visible.

III. Represent Explicit Mitigation Efforts.

- Just like noting potential biases associated with channels, also note efforts to mitigate biases which might be present.
- This might involve removal of certain information, normalization, control-steps, human-in-the-loop or other methods.
- It might not be clear before impact analysis if a certain operation is mitigating or causing bias.
- Presence of these efforts do not guarantee that they are effective.

Result: An annotated IFM that identifies and categorizes potential biases, providing a foundation for mitigation strategies and impact analysis.

Step 5: Connecting Stakeholders and Impacts

This step connects the information flow model to real-world consequences by identifying affected stakeholders and tracing how outcomes, decisions, or biases in the system may impact them. The IFM provides the structural traceability to link modeled transformations to concrete harms, benefits, or risks experienced by different groups.

While this method does not prescribe a fixed framework for stakeholder or risk analysis, it provides the necessary scaffolding to apply such methods meaningfully. The following actions can be taken within the IFM context:

I. Identify and Categorize Stakeholders

- **Identify Stakeholders:** Determine who is directly or indirectly affected by the system. For example, applicants, evaluators, decision-makers, or service recipients.
- **Categorize Stakeholders:** Group stakeholders into categories relevant to the domain or use case (e.g., successful vs. rejected applicants, vulnerable groups, oversight actors).
- *Consider if sub-groups of stakeholders might be affected differently by the same outcome. By considering both legally protected categories and case-specific groups and potentially intersections between them less visible or indirect stakeholder-groups can be discovered.*

II. Trace Potential Impacts Through the IFM

- Identify which outputs or decisions which can contribute to stakeholder impacts.
- Use the graph to follow these Impacts backwards through the IFM flow how transformations propagate toward stakeholder-relevant outcomes.
- This creates paths of impact upstreams through the IFM, annotate these paths by their impacts.
- Use the bias annotations from Step 4 to follow the propagation of bias downstreams, similarly creating paths.
- Identify how these paths of bias and paths of impact intersect and interact to affect stakeholders or sub-groups of stakeholders.
- If mitigation or compensatory measures are present, include them in the traced paths.

Result: A stakeholder-annotated IFM that supports reasoning about impact distribution, accountability, and fairness. This structure enables integration with domain-specific methods for harm evaluation, redress planning, or compliance assessment.

Step 6: Evaluating Mitigation and Design Options

The final step involves using the resulting model in order to assess the decision making system or explore strategies to address the biases and impacts identified in the previous steps. This includes applying targeted assessment methods and analyses, considering design improvements, and targeted mitigation measures.

I. Design Improvements

- Eliminate or clarify ambiguities and alternatives in the IFM.
- Modify or remove channels that introduce known biases.
- Introduce additional control steps to improve decision-making transparency and fairness.

II. Additional Assessment Methods

- Use statistical tests and fairness metrics to confirm the presence and severity of biases.
- Simulate alternative scenarios with synthetic data to evaluate potential outcomes.

III. Mitigation Measures

- Apply fairness techniques, such as reweighting or post-hoc adjustments, to address biases.
- Constrain mitigation efforts to channels or decisions linked to material stakeholder impacts.
- Monitor for unintended consequences, such as adverse effects on other stakeholder groups.

Result: A set of prioritized design, assessment, and mitigation strategies that address identified biases and minimize stakeholder impacts.